

MODERN ACHIEVEMENTS IN PANCREAS SURGERY.

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Relevance:

Significant progress in surgery in recent decades has not had much impact on the increase in the number of radical operations for pancreaticoduodenal cancer. Meanwhile, there has been a steady increase in the incidence of cancer of the pancreas (P) and organs of the periampullary zone, and due to radio- and chemoresistance of tumors of this localization, the only radical method of treatment remains surgical.

Key words: Pancreas surgery, prostate cancer.

Introduction:

Today, pancreatic cancer remains one of the most serious diseases with a poor prognosis. Patients with stage III tumor growth live no more than 3 months; inoperable patients account for more than 85% [6, 9]. The incidence of pancreatic cancer over the past 30 years in our country has increased by 30% and is 9.5 men and 7.6 women per 100,000 population [3]. Late diagnosis leads to low resectability. It ranges from 4 to 15%. The relevance of the problem is also due to the fact that the disease more often affects people of working age (from 40 to 60 years), in the early stages it is difficult to diagnose, often aggravated by obstructive jaundice, and surgical treatment consists of a technically complex and very traumatic pancreaticoduodenectomy. The five-year survival rate of patients with pancreatic cancer averages 2.5–15% [9, 12]. Late diagnosis and the associated low percentage of resectability, along with high postoperative mortality, explain the unfounded opinion about the futility of surgical treatment for tumors of the pancreaticoduodenal zone. This is associated with the frequent refusal of radical operations for patients or the limitation of surgical intervention to palliative biliodigestive anastomoses, after which the mortality rate is 20–60%, and the life expectancy of patients rarely exceeds 4.5–6 months [6]. Types of radical surgical interventions for tumors of the pancreaticoduodenal zone: • Pancreaticoduodenal resection (Whipple operation). • Distal pancreatectomy. • Sectoral (partial) resection of the pancreas, • Total duodenopancreatectomy. • Extended sub- or total pancreatectomy (including regional resection of the pancreas, combined resection

of the pancreas). • Pylorus-preserving PDR. The main type of radical surgery for malignant tumors emanating from the head of the pancreas and adjacent organs of the pancreaticoduodenal zone (major duodenal papilla (MDP) of the duodenum, terminal part of the common bile duct, is pancreaticoduodenal resection (PDR), which in its classic version provides (Whipple operation,

Annals of surgical hepatology. 1999. T. 4. No. 2 P. 13-22 1935) removal of a complex of organs, including the head of the pancreas, the entire duodenum or most of it, in most cases the antrum of the stomach, the distal part of the common bile duct. With the accumulation of experience, a number of disadvantages of this operation have emerged, the most important of which are recognized as: • Insufficient radicalism, in particular in pancreatic cancer (on average 10-20% according to various authors); • A significant number of complications (at least 40%), primarily associated with the failure of pancreatojejunostomy and necrosis of the pancreatic stump. Summarizing the results of PDR according to various authors, it should be noted that the resectability of tumors of the pancreaticoduodenal zone ranges from 4-27% (on average 15%), postoperative mortality even in the most progressive clinics reaches 8-22%, and the five-year survival rate is about 4- 6% [7, 9, 12, 18, 19, 69]. These circumstances have given grounds for a number of authors to recommend total duodenopancreatectomy (TDPE) instead of PDR for cancer of the organs of the periampullary zone and, first of all, the head of the pancreas [41]. With TDPE, as indicated by supporters of its wider use (Van Heerden J., 1984, Moossa A.R., 1993, Launois V., 1993, etc.), the danger of leaving tumor tissue in the pancreatic stump is eliminated, which, according to various estimates (Ander- Sanberg A., 1983, Longmire W., 1984) after PDR ranges from 18 to 45% of cases [2]. Indications for performing TDPE: 1. diffuse pancreatic carcinomatosis (6%), 2. multicentric tumors (12% of patients), 3. chronic recurrent pancreatitis, 4. spread of pancreatic head cancer to its body (or detection of tumor cells along the resection border during urgent intraoperative morphological examination after completion of PDR), 5. pronounced pathological changes in the pancreatic stump and main pancreatic duct, which do not allow the application of pancreatodigestive anastomosis or occlusion of the ducts of the pancreatic stump. The TDPE technique includes the corresponding stages of PDR and distal pancreatic resection [2]. In typical cases, the entire complex of organs is isolated as a single block. During mobilization of the tail of the pancreas and spleen, the short vessels of the stomach can also be ligated, and therefore almost the entire greater curvature of the stomach is devascularized. Taking this into account, with TDPE the volume of gastric resection usually reaches from 2/3 to 3/4, exceeding that with PDR. Like PDR, pancreatic extirpation is not necessarily accompanied by gastric resection; a surgical technique that preserves the stomach and pylorus can be used. In this case, in particular, it is necessary to preserve the arcade of the gastroepiploic arteries. In the process of mobilization of the pancreas, isolation, isolated ligation and division of the splenic artery near its mouth and the splenic vein near its confluence with the superior mesenteric are of key importance [2]. The course of the inferior mesenteric vein is traced. After this stage and the previously performed mobilization of the pancreaticoduodenal

complex, the iron remains fixed, mainly by its uncinat process and its own ligament, which are separated from the superior mesenteric (portal) vein, ligated and cut off. The reconstructive stage of TDPE is less complicated than in PDR and includes the creation of only two anastomoses - biliodigestive and gastrointestinal, the formation technique of which corresponds to that used in PDR. Anastomoses can be sequentially applied to one initial loop of jejunum. However, with a small diameter of the hepaticocholedochus, thinning and fragility of its wall, which creates the risk of insufficiency of the bile-ducting anastomosis, it is more advisable to separate the anastomoses by using a long small intestinal loop isolated by a Y-shaped anastomosis for biliodigestive.

Annals of surgical hepatology. 1999. T. 4. No. 2 P. 13-22 Moreover, long-term results indicate the effectiveness of extended PE even in cases where regional metastasis to the lymph nodes or invasion of the portal/superior mesenteric veins (PV/SMV) was noted. In an effort to improve the treatment outcomes of such patients, extended PE, in this regard, should be actively used in practice [5, 24, 42, 49]. Ishikawa O. [31] and Nagakawa T. [52] independently showed that the results of surgical intervention in the long-term period are prognostically favorable in patients with a tumor lesion size of 4 cm in diameter or less (or with larger sizes, but with provided there is no germination of the pancreas capsule); in the absence of tumor invasion into regional lymph nodes (or single metastatic foci in regional lymph nodes - damage to no more than 0-3 groups of regional lymph nodes); when limiting tumor growth within the pancreaticoduodenal region; with unilateral invasion of the PV/SMV no more than 2 cm; in the absence of invasion into the main arterial lines. In part, these conditions can be assessed preoperatively using ultrasound echography, endoscopic ultrasonography, Doppler ultrasound, contrast computed tomography, nuclear magnetic resonance, angiography, endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography, percutaneous transhepatic cholangiostomy and -graphy, puncture cytobiopsy, laparoscopy. Data from intraoperative histological and cytological studies, ultrasound and Doppler diagnostics clarify the degree of spread of the tumor process. The key stage of performing extended PE (according to Ishikawa O. et al. [31]) is skeletonization of the main vascular structures on the left and back for complete revision and removal of surrounding fiber and tissue. Unlike the traditional mobilization of the duodenum according to Kocher, in which only the duodenum and the head of the pancreas are released, when using this method of retroperitoneal organ release, a more thorough sanitation of the surrounding tissues, cellular spaces and lymphatic collectors is achieved. Taking into account the fact that lymphatic drainage from the posterior surface of the pancreas and its head, as well as from the pericastric/superior mesenteric region, is carried out predominantly into the para-aortic lymphatic collectors, which are regional second-order lymph nodes [33, 50, 51], the optimal boundaries of retroperitoneal mobilization are as follows: right the border corresponds to the right edge of the inferior vena cava; left - 2-3 cm outward from the left edge of the aorta; the upper border is 2 cm above the celiac trunk; the mouth of the inferior mesenteric artery corresponds to the lower border of skeletonization (Fig. 1). Mobilization and excision of the muscular structures around the aorta facilitate visualization of the celiac axis. The duodenum

is completely mobilized up to the ligament of Treitz. The right half of the greater omentum is separated from the transverse colon. Vascular collaterals running from the mesentery of the transverse colon to the lower edge of the head of the pancreas are also ligated¹. The right colon vein is isolated retrogradely up to its junction with the SMV. The author does not recommend tissue separation (the so-called tunnelization) between the anterior surface of the portal and SMV, as well as the posterior surface of the cervical pancreas; It is preferable to remove the head of the pancreas with the tumor focus in combination with IV/SVV².

The technique of sectoral resection of the head of the pancreas in a number of stages is similar to subtotal and classic PDR. At the stage of isolating the head of the pancreas, special attention is paid to maintaining the blood supply to the duodenum (Danilov M.V., Russell R.C.G Kimura W.). For this purpose, in particular, when opening the omental bursa, they strive to avoid damage to the gastroepiploic arteries. The duodenum is mobilized according to Kocher, while the separation of dense widespread adhesions around the intestine often makes it possible to eliminate the narrowing of the intestinal tube and restore its patency. The superior mesenteric vein is isolated below, and, if possible, above the isthmus of the gland, which, after creating a tunnel under it, is placed on a rubber holder. It is advisable to isolate the common hepatic artery over the upper edge of the gland and the common bile duct in the hepatoduodenal ligament, also taking them on supports. The stage of sectoral resection of the pancreas begins with the intersection of its isthmus above the mesenteric-portal venous trunk, and hemostasis of the distal stump of the gland is performed with entwining or interrupted sutures. The head of the pancreas together with the DP is turned to the right and the trunk of the SMV/PV is separated from the right edge, tying off the small vascular branches flowing into it. When resection of the head of the pancreas, according to Beger N. (1990), there is no need to preserve the gastroduodenal artery, since its ligation does not disrupt the blood supply of the duodenum. The intrapancreatic part of the common bile duct is isolated to the point of its confluence with the main pancreatic duct. For orientation, it is advisable to insert a metal probe into the hepaticocholedochus through the choledochotomy opening or the stump of the cystic duct. After cutting off the preparation, the dorsal duodenopancreatic arterial arch, which provides blood supply to the wall of the duodenum and the common bile duct, should be preserved. The reconstructive stage of the operation includes the creation of an anastomosis of the distal stump of the pancreas with a loop of jejunum isolated according to Roux, using the “end to end” or “end to side” type. In the presence of strictures along the duct of the corpocaudal part of the pancreas, H. Beger (1990) recommends applying a longitudinal extended pancreaticojejunostomy. Treatment of the duct of the remaining small proximal stump of the pancreas can be done using various methods. Dobryakov B.B. (1985) recommends bandaging it; Beger N. (1990) prefers to anastomose it in isolation with the same loop of jejunum that was used for anastomosis with the distal stump of the gland. In most cases, biliodigestive bypass is not required, since the isolation of the common bile duct from the tissue of the head of the pancreas ensures its sufficient decompression. Currently, the use of this type of organ-preserving proximal resection of the pancreas is generally accompanied by favorable immediate outcomes, as

well as quite satisfactory functional results, in particular, the preservation or increase of body weight in the majority of operated patients and the absence of pronounced postoperative dysfunction of the insular apparatus.

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